

Analysis of the Formation and Development of Anti-Narcotics Cadres to Prevent and Overcome the Impact of Narcotics According to the Narcotics Law Number 9 of 1999 on Minors in Medan Johor District, Medan City, North Sumatra Province

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to describes the object that is the main problem and analyzes it with the aim of drawing a conclusion. Because it is hoped that it will be able to provide a detailed, systematic and comprehensive description of the object of study to be researched. As for other things, there is a lack of treatment for underage drug addicts, as well as the lack of costs to bring in resource persons and internet access to obtain information regarding types of narcotics, prevention, action, treatment by rehabilitating victims due to narcotics addiction and punitive sanctions for those who violate the law. Narcotics No.35 of 2009. So in Medan Johor District, North Sumatra Province, the Community Service Team from Dharmawangsa University felt that it was very necessary to carry out outreach regarding the Implementation of Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 on the dangers as well as their formation and handling in Medan Johor District, so that with socialization, the Service Team hopes to be right on target with the community by providing information regarding dangers, forming volunteers, posts for public complaints and narcotics abuse, as well as matters relating to the formation of anti-narcotics volunteers and information regarding procedures for forming, overcoming and rehabilitating victims of narcotics addiction.

INTRODUCTION

There are Narcotics problems which are increasingly widespread, especially in Medan Johor District, after carrying out socialization/counseling, the community service team has carried out material training entitled "Implementation of the Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 on Dangers and their Handling, Establishment of Volunteers and Anti-Drug Posts against narcotics addicts, in accordance with SEMA Number 4 of 2010 dated 07 April 2010", delivered by Maysarah.SH.MH,-. The material entitled "Economic Impact for Drug Users", Dr. Ariman Sitompul.MH, Material entitled "The Role of Interpersonal Communication for Drug Sufferers and Their Families", and Material entitled "Trends in Narcotics Abuse in Indonesia", Counseling and Socialization have been carried out and have received a positive response from participants, this can be seen from the level of attendance and questions asked by participants during the material presented, assessment of anti-narcotics volunteers.

The legal impact for drug addicts and users on minors must be implemented, to avoid preventing minors from taking drugs, who need extra supervision. Those who do not receive rehabilitation services from the state from an early age must be prevented by carrying out outreach aimed at forming anti-drug volunteers and recruiting volunteers and establishing complaint posts as users or perpetrators of drug trafficking crimes, which will result in increasing the population of several sub-districts in Medan Johor District has around 20 people and this may even increase if we deploy village officials to collect samples from this population.

How to prevent and deal with drug trafficking and addiction is the absence of narcotics volunteers and lack of supervision from the authorities. The method for implementing this Community Service is by carrying out: Implementation Method, Implementation Method, Participatory Method and Approach Method. Apart from that, the team also carried out observation or interview methods, documentation, and survey activities to find out what were the problems. Based on the problems above and the importance of community service carried out by various government agencies as well as universities and other institutions that can carry out outreach related to narcotics in Medan Johor District, the proposing team offers a solution to the problem to audience members, namely 1. Providing education and socializing about implementation Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning narcotics, 2. Providing education and socializing the importance of therapeutic communication for victims of narcotics abuse. 3. Providing outreach and education about the influence of narcotics on the economy of victims of narcotics abuse by implementing Mayor Regulation Number 5 of 2021 concerning community services by forming anti-drug volunteers and cadres from the neighborhood level to the Medan Johor District level, by making use of existing facilities and infrastructure in around Medan Johor District, such as places of worship and homes for volunteers as well as the homes of community servants, as well as SK-Ka Subdistrict management.

As for other things, there is a lack of treatment for underage drug addicts, as well as the lack of costs to bring in resource persons and internet access to obtain information regarding types of narcotics, prevention, action, treatment by rehabilitating victims due to narcotics addiction and punitive sanctions for those who violate the law. Narcotics No.35 of 2009. So in Medan Johor District, North Sumatra Province, the Community Service Team from Dharmawagsa University felt that it was very necessary to carry out outreach regarding the Implementation of Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 on the dangers as well as their formation and handling in Medan Johor District, so that with socialization, the Service Team hopes to be right on target with the community by providing information regarding dangers, forming volunteers, posts for public complaints and narcotics abuse, as well as matters relating to the formation of anti-narcotics volunteers and information regarding procedures for forming, overcoming and rehabilitating victims of narcotics addiction. Due to the dense population in the Medan Johor District area. Which has a population of 151,756 people, with an area of 14.58 km² and a population density of 10,409 people/km². Within its area there is a Medan Embarkation Hajj Dormitory Building, several government offices, a General Hospital, several Housewares and several schools as well as several community businesses that are also developing, such as restaurants, workshops, pharmacies, supermarkets and so on. By looking at the fairly advanced development of Medan Johor District, not only is the population potential growing, economic factors are also developing, therefore the level of social inequality in the population is also increasing. Most addicts and users of narcotics (drugs) started with weakening economic factors and a level of depression in them, such as the desire to get rich quickly, a weak level of education and a high imagination of wanting to achieve like the people in their environment in an instant way. Finally, use the short route. Become a dealer of prohibited goods. Not only is it dangerous for itself but it can also damage the environment where it lives. It is commonplace among social disparities that occur in developing regions. One's level of economic progress influences the level of the lower economy so that the difference in level triggers instant thinking to balance a weak economy with a strong one. In the end, what was taken was an instant path which was actually dangerous. Like being a drug dealer. The opportunity to carry it out is very free, environmental conditions permit and socialization is also lacking. As a result, the spread of drugs is slowly becoming more widespread in Medan Johor District.

Due to the dense population in the Medan Johor District area. There is a Medan Embarkation Hajj Dormitory Building, several government offices, a General Hospital, several Housewares and several schools. Looking at the existing potential, Medan Johor sub-district is a developing area with a dense population capacity so that there are many potential opportunities that can develop within it. As in the trade sector, many people's businesses are developing, such as restaurants, supermarkets, workshops, and so on. Organizations or community associations are also growing rapidly. Based on BPS data for Medan City in 2020, the occupation of residents of this sub-district

consists of 24,699 private employees, 10,440 traders, 4,336 Civil Servants (PNS), 2,094 farmers, 2,284 entrepreneurs and 12,071 retirees. Some of the facilities in Medan Johor District include:

- Asrama Haji Pangkalan Mansyur
- Laboratorium Percobaan Pertanian Fakultas Pertanian Universitas Islam Sumatra Utara
- Balai Pengkajian Tanaman Pangan Provinsi Sumatra Utara
- Taman Cadika Pramuka: Pusat Pendidikan & Pelatihan Pramuka Kwartir Cabang Kota Medan
- STMIK Triguna Dharma
- Masjid Baiturrahmah
- Masjid Baitul Iman
- Masjid Annazhirin
- Balai Diklat Keuangan Kementerian Keuangan - Jl.Eka Warni
- Perhubungan Daerah Militer I/Bukit Barisan (Hubdam I/BB)
- Kanal Banjir Medan
- Baterai P Batalyon Artileri Pertahanan Udara Sedang (Yon Arhanudse) 11/BS
- Lapangan Sejati
- Pasar Johor
- Chykes Swalayan
- Diamond Swalayan
- J. City

By looking at the fairly advanced development of Medan Johor District, not only is the population potential growing, economic factors are also developing, therefore the level of social inequality in the population is also increasing. Most addicts and users of narcotics (drugs) started with weakening economic factors and a level of depression in them, such as the desire to get rich quickly, a weak level of education and a high imagination of wanting to achieve like the people in their environment in an instant way. Finally, use the short route. Become a dealer of prohibited goods. Not only is it dangerous for itself but it can also damage the environment where it lives. It is commonplace among social disparities that occur in developing regions. One's level of economic progress influences the level of the lower economy so that the difference in level triggers instant thinking to balance a weak economy with a strong one. In the end, what was taken was an instant path which was actually dangerous. Like being a drug dealer. The opportunity to carry it out is very free, environmental conditions permit and socialization is also lacking. As a result, the spread of drugs is slowly becoming more widespread in Medan Johor District.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

In this normative juridical research, researchers will carry out data collection and analysis of laws and regulations related to narcotics, as well as

evaluate the suitability and consistency of these practices with the Narcotics Law No. 35 of 2009.

Normative and empirical juridical research can provide a clear picture regarding the implementation method used, namely the counseling/guidance method (bimtek) starting with observation (interviews with village heads, sub-district heads, religious figures/scholars, the community and the Medan Johor sub-district head), the theory presented 3 (three), namely 1. Theory of Justice, 2. Theory of Legal Certainty and 3. Theory of Maqasid Syariah, and this research also examines children at awash age as narcotics addicts, the researcher also offers and provides 3 (three) sources, who is a research team as well as a community service team, not only researching but at the same time disseminating information and conducting discussions, re-evaluating the program presented by the resource persons, monitoring the results which are socialized and continuously distributed to the participants and the community, by sharing the personal contacts of the resource persons, so that socialization continues to be sustainable, and the public receives information services at any time, as well as providing a clearer view of the legal effects that will occur if violations or unlawful actions occur.

In the context of legal studies regarding the implementation of Narcotics Law No. 35 of 2009, normative juridical research can make an important contribution in helping determine a clear and objective legal view of the case, as well as providing recommendations on the steps that need to be taken in resolving the case. .

METHODOLOGY

This research is a descriptive research. Descriptive research aims to accurately describe the characteristics of an individual, situation, symptom or certain group, to determine whether there is a relationship between a symptom and other symptoms in society. Descriptive research is research that merely describes objects or events without any intention of drawing generally applicable conclusions. This research aims to review the parties involved in industrial relations.

This research is descriptive analytical, namely research that only describes the object that is the main problem and analyzes it with the aim of drawing a conclusion. Because it is hoped that it will be able to provide a detailed, systematic and comprehensive description of the object of study to be researched.

This type of research is included in qualitative research, namely research that seeks to find legal symptoms that are developing in a community related to this research through the results of interviews, questionnaires and other official documents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data analysis process begins by reviewing all available data from various sources. The main sources in this research are primary and secondary data. The data analysis system used in this research is to process primary data which is then compared with secondary data to see whether the theory used is

correct, so that it can be seen whether there is a legal vacuum, blurred meaning, legal inequality or inconsistency that occurs in Medan Johor District with legislation. In short, to find out whether there are differences or problems that occur between primary and secondary data. All data that has been obtained is then processed and reduced for analysis, from the 3 (three) theories applied.

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A partnership has been established between Dharmawangsa University and Medan Johor District, in the form of Danger and Cure, which has an impact on the economy of narcotics addicts/users and the establishment of anti-narcotics posts in Medan Johor District. This activity was welcomed positively and enthusiastically by the participants, because the participants are members of the public who have the widest opportunity to participate and help prevent and eradicate the abuse and illicit trafficking of narcotics and narcotics precursors (Articles 104, 106 and 108 of Law Number 35 of 2009), however, the community does not have the right to arrest and detain, but the community is only a volunteer who assists the main tasks of the National Narcotics Agency and the Narcotics Unit in the Police Institution, as well as how to implement Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics towards criminals. narcotics addicts, are they in accordance with its implementation?, which basically they have never received Socialization Training on the Implementation of Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009. Dangers and their Management, in Medan Johor District, especially for narcotics addicts, so that with this socialization the participants become a comprehensive and sustainable society in eradicating narcotics.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Sociology of Islamic law is a social science that studies legal phenomena which aims to provide an explanation of the legal practices of science that regulates the reciprocal relationship between various social phenomena in Muslim society as creatures that adhere strictly to Islamic law.

The scope of legal sociology includes: First, patterns of behavior (law) of community members. Second, laws and patterns of behavior as creations and manifestations of social groups. Third, the reciprocal relationship between

changes in law and social and cultural changes or the scope of the study is the current laws that apply in society.

The aim of studying the sociology of Islamic law is to find out the social symptoms of Muslim society as legal subjects who position law as a guide to life. Studying the sociology of Islamic law can also find out the extent of the effectiveness of Islamic law in governing Muslim society and of course you can also find out about legal changes that are developing.

Sociology of Islamic law has a sociological scope which has the aim of studying the sociology of Islamic law where the law will be applied in society, so that the aim of studying it is to know the extent to which the sociology of Islamic law is effective and the effectiveness of positive law, the extent to which it is experiencing change and development in Indonesia. So here the author feels that this scientific work really needs suggestions and criticism so that this scientific work is more interesting so that it can be thoroughly explored and applied in all aspects of life in subsequent scientific works.

The team also conveyed the solution to the problem to the participants and partners, namely: The Proposing Team will carry out socialization and training (Bimtek), regarding the Implementation of Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics at the next meeting, if Partners and the community want the drug problem to be resolved in Their Village. The Proposing Team will provide socialization, education and training (Bimtek) about the importance of establishing a post (this post is formed if BNN does not yet have one and is available) provide and receive information and communication about narcotics addicts, and the Proposing Team will provide socialization, education / Insight and training (Bimtek) which relates to the importance of providing medical and non-medical services for narcotics addicts. The aim of this is so that cooperation with partners continues to be sustainable, so that there are no victims of human rights violations for narcotics addicts from a legal perspective, no more people are harmed as narcotics addicts from a health and economic perspective. The understanding and counseling given to the community has a positive impact on people who previously did not understand, now they understand both in terms of law, communication and economics. This is a sense of satisfaction for the Devotion team and hopes that the partner relationship will continue.

The implementation of this community service activity has proceeded according to the planned schedule. From the research activities that have been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. The Law Study Program's community service team has successfully carried out training with the roles and duties of each team in providing material. There is great hope for the service team so that people whose families have been affected or have not been affected by the narcotics vortex will properly understand the law, communication and economic impacts for users and dealers.
2. The approach taken in this research can of course be a benchmark for the community in anticipating the spread of narcotics in their area to no longer exist, because if left unchecked it will have an impact on the growth and development of the next generation. It is hoped that the

understanding and counseling that the team provides can help the public understand the dangers of narcotics in terms of law, communication and economics. Where Mitra's problems before the PKM team arrived was the lack of educational outreach, technical guidance (Bimtek) regarding the implementation of Narcotics Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning narcotics, the importance of therapeutic communication for victims of narcotics abuse, the influence of narcotics on the economy of victims of narcotics abuse. This is what makes us provide community service in Medan Johor District.

3. The team also conveyed the solution to the problem to the participants and partners, namely: The Proposing Team will carry out socialization and training (Bimtek), regarding the Implementation of Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics at the next meeting, if Partners and the community want the drug problem to be resolved. complete it in their village. The Proposing Team will provide socialization, education and training (Bimtek) about the importance of establishing a post (this post is formed if BNN does not yet have one and is available) provide and receive information and communication about narcotics addicts, and the Proposing Team will provide socialization, education / Insight and training (Bimtek) which relates to the importance of providing medical and non-medical services for narcotics addicts. The aim of this is so that cooperation with partners continues to be sustainable, so that there are no victims of human rights violations for narcotics addicts from a legal perspective, no more people are harmed as narcotics addicts from a health and economic perspective. The understanding and counseling given to the community has a positive impact on people who previously did not understand, now they understand both in terms of law, communication and economics. This is a sense of satisfaction for the research team and hopes that the partner relationship will continue.

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